

parts withered, dried, and ruptured along the streaks, causing a blighted appearance

The feeding activity of adult beetles was recorded at 0900, 1200, and 1600

hours on a clear, sunny day. Adult beetle feeding was maximum (44%) at 0900; it was lowest (3%) at 1200 and intermediate (26.8%) at 1600 hours.

major insect pests of irrigated rice are the fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Smith and Abb.), the brown semilooper *Mocis latipes* (Guen.), the rice water weevil *Lissorhoptrus* sp., and the stink bug *Oebalus poecilus* (Dall). These insect populations must be controlled if rice is to be grown profitably. The table shows pest occurrence in relation to the growth stage of the rice plant.

Major insect pests of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin

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About 4,000 ha of irrigated rice producing 2 crops/year is cultivated in the Jari estate on the northern side of the Amazon River, between the Paru and Jari Rivers. IR22 is commercially grown in the area. The first crop is planted in April–May and harvested in August–September, then the second crop is planted and harvested in December–January. Field operations are completely mechanized; large machinery and agricultural aircraft are used.

The cultivated area has increased in the past few years and the double-cropping system has recently been adopted. Consequently, insect pests are becoming serious. Field surveys show that the

Major insect pests of irrigated rice in the lower Amazon Basin, Brazil.

Rice growth stage	Major insect pests		Damage
	1st crop	2d crop	
Seedling emergence to maximum tillering	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	<i>S. frugiperda</i>	Leaf feeding
	<i>Mocis latipes</i>	–	Leaf feeding
	<i>Lissorhoptrus</i> sp.	<i>Lissorhoptrus</i>	Leaf feeding (adults) and root pruning (larvae)
Panicle initiation to heading	<i>Mocis latipes</i>	–	Leaf feeding and head damage
Heading to dough	<i>Oebalus poecilus</i>	<i>O. poecilus</i>	Grain sucking (nymphs and adults)

Effects of granular insecticides on stem borers and their parasites and predators

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Granular insecticide formulations tend to be effective for the control of rice stem borers and brown planthoppers in Thailand.

An experiment was conducted at the Chainat Rice Experiment Station, Chainat province, to determine the effectiveness of granular insecticide formulations for stem borer control, their adverse effects on stem borer parasites and predators, and the expected monetary returns from treated vs check plots.

Three granular insecticides — lindane 6% G, chlorfenvinphos 10%, carbofuran 3% G — were tested on variety RD1, which is susceptible to stem borers. They were applied at 1 kg a.i./ha 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting.

A split-plot design with three replications was used, with insecticide rates as the main plot and insecticide as subplots. A compound fertilizer of

Table 1. Effects of granular insecticides applied at 1 kg a.i./ha 20, 40, and 60 days after transplanting (DT) on stem borers, and that on predators and parasites. Chainat, Thailand, 1976.

Treatment	Effect of insecticide		
	20 DT	40 DT	60 DT
	<i>Stem borers</i> ^a		
Lindane	2.50	28.50	92.33
Chlorfenvinphos	3.33	22.00	32.00
Carbofuran	0.50	7.50	7.50
Check	7.67	41.83	17.00
LSD 0.05	NS	1.37	1.71
C.V.	57.0%	23.2%	19.1%
	<i>Predators</i> ^b		
Lindane	6.17	63.83	69.83
Chlorfenvinphos	9.83	43.83	38.17
Carbofuran	4.83	12.83	6.33
Check	15.17	56.00	85.67
LSD 0.05	0.85	1.00	1.09
C.V.	23.8%	12.6%	13.3%
	<i>Parasites</i> ^c		
Lindane	4.67	2.50	3.17
Chlorfenvinphos	5.33	4.83	6.00
Carbofuran	6.17	3.67	2.67
Check	8.50	6.83	6.50
LSD 0.07	0.53	NS	NS
C.V.	17.5%	2.7.0%	29.2%

^a Stem borer infestation based on % dead hearts. The predominant species of stem borer were *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) and *Chilo polychrysus* (Meyrick). ^b No./10 sweeps of sweeping net 42 cm in diam. The predators were *Tetragnatha* spp., *Oxyopes* spp., *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* (Reuter), *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, and damselflies. ^c No./10 sweeps of sweeping net 42 cm in diam. The parasites were *Telenomus* spp., *Apanteles* spp., *Tetrastichus* spp., *Elasmus* spp., and *Tropobracon* spp.